

PRESS RELEASE

June 2025

New European Network Launched to Boost Short Food Supply Chains

Brussels – A new European initiative is bringing together advisors, experts, and policymakers in a pioneering move to strengthen short food supply chains (SFSCs) across the continent. Led by [EU4Advice](#) and [COREnet](#), the initiative aims to build more resilient, transparent, and sustainable food systems across Europe. The two networks are co-developed and jointly supported by both projects.

This effort comes at a crucial time, as an increasing number of farmers and food producers seek alternatives to lengthy and complex supply chains. The network is particularly relevant to those working to help producers sell directly to consumers, increase their bargaining power, and adopt more socially and environmentally responsible production models.

The initiative comprises two complementary elements. The first is a **SCSC European advisory network** offering dedicated training, access to curated resources, and opportunities for knowledge exchange and collaboration across borders. Advisors and food system experts are invited to join a dynamic, EU-wide community that provides thematic workshops, shared learning spaces, and increased visibility through a publicly accessible database of SFSC professionals. One of the objectives of EU4Advice is to integrate SFSC-related advisory services, tools and contents into national Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation Systems (AKIS)

Participation also opens the door to contributing directly to EU-level policy recommendations aimed at strengthening the SFSC sector.

According to [Fedele Colantuono](#), coordinator of the COREnet project, more than 500 advisors and experts from all EU member states have already joined the Network. *“We’re building a growing ecosystem where peer-to-peer learning and innovation are central,” he said. “Alongside our COREnet Golden Cases—designed to replicate successful SFSC models—we’ve recently launched an open call for Lighthouse Projects to offer registered advisors new opportunities to scale bold ideas.”*

The second component is a newly launched **network for policymakers** committed to building fairer and more sustainable food systems. This space provides regional, national, and local public authorities with the opportunity to connect directly with their

counterparts across Europe, share challenges and solutions, and engage with producers, advisors, researchers, and key AKIS stakeholders.

[Patricia Mora](#), coordinator of EU4Advice, emphasised the importance of bridging technical expertise and political decision-making. *“Through this dual-network approach, we’re creating stronger links between those who shape policy and those who implement it. It’s about ensuring local food systems have the tools and support they need to thrive.”*

Joining the networks is entirely voluntary and designed to accommodate different levels of involvement. Those interested in registering can do so through the dedicated online forms: the [Advisors’ Form](#) and the [Policymakers’ Form](#).

About EU4Advice

EU4Advice is a Horizon Europe-funded project designed to strengthen short food supply chains (SFSCs) across Europe by empowering advisory services and promoting knowledge exchange among key stakeholders. The project works to enhance the capacity of advisors, improve collaboration between producers, researchers, and policymakers, and support the transition toward more sustainable, resilient, and socially equitable food systems. There are four Living Labs established as part of the project, located in Spain, the Netherlands, Hungary, and Ireland. They co-create and test practical solutions for short food supply chains (SFSCs), enabling continuous learning and feedback throughout the project's five-year duration.

About COREnet:

The COREnet project, a Horizon EU-funded initiative coordinated by the University of Foggia, focuses on Short Food Supply Chains (SFSCs), which contribute to more inclusive, resilient, and sustainable food systems. The project aims to enhance the development and scalability of SFSCs through collaborative knowledge sharing among stakeholders. The project will integrate SFSC guidance into the Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation Systems (AKIS), informing policy recommendations at the EU level, supporting advisors with new tools, and disseminating innovative solutions.

Contact information:

Raquel Carro, EU4Advice Project Manager. raquel@australo.org

Leonardo Impronta, COREnet Communication and Dissemination leader.
leonardo.impronta@icons.it